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Why is abatement of flue gas emissions important?

Initiatives for abatement

SO₂

- Scrubber for removal of SO₂.

Particles

- Filters
 - Electrostatic particle removal.

NO_x

- Selective catalytic reduction. Produces N₂O.

N₂O

- None

Emissions in Denmark

1987

SO₂: 163.000 tons
 NO_x: 129.000 tons

2008

SO₂: 5.000 tons
 NO_x: 20.000 tons

N₂O

Lifetime: 150 years in the atmosphere.

Catalyst for ozone degradation.

Greenhouse gas: 300 times more potent than CO₂.

Conclusions

Abatement of flue gas emissions is important to protect the environment.

There is no legislation on the abatement of N₂O emissions.

A tandem SCR-deN₂O module can remove NO_x gases more efficiently than contemporary solutions.

Novel catalysts

SCR

15 % V₂O₅ on TiO₂
 First-order rate constant: 2150 (commercial: 854)
 Resistant to alkali poisoning.

Analysis methods:
 FT-IR, Raman, XPS, ESR

Conclusions:
 Highly disperse, high loading, robust.

deN₂O

CoNi oxide
 100 % conversion at 300-350 °C

Analysis methods:
 XPS

Conclusions:
 Highly disperse, alkali promoter is at surface.

References

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